

CHARACTERISATION OF EPOXY NETWORKS RESINS DERIVED FROM NOVEL AMINE HARDENERS

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Keywords: Epoxy, amine, Structure/property relationships, Toughness, Synthesis

ABSTRACT

Tri-aryl ether and ketone amine isomers with varying meta and para aromatic substitution have been cured with a commercially available diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F epoxy resin. The mechanical and thermal properties, as well as reaction rates have been characterised and are related to specific changes in the aryl linkage groups and substitution patterns. In the case of the rate of reaction, inductive and resonance effects, from the strongly electron donating ether groups increase amine reactivity while conversely the electron withdrawing carbonyl groups reduce amine reactivity. With respect to thermal and mechanical properties, comparative molecular mobility within the rigid networks controls the mechanical and thermal properties. The carbonyl group increases T_g , char yield, modulus and strength, whilst reducing displacement at yield. Regardless of chemical linkage, increasing para substitution increased T_g and displacement at failure, whilst reducing strength and stiffness. The insights gained from this work, provide new pathways towards the rational design of a new generation of epoxy amine networks with improved processability, strength, stiffness and ductility.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are used in a wide range of structural applications due to their high strength to weight ratio, but are also well known for their lack of toughness, leading to delamination or poor impact resistance in the final composite or component. Many studies have therefore been devoted to improving their toughness through the addition of modifiers such as rubbers, thermoplastics, nano-additives to name but a few [1]. Despite successfully improving the toughness of the composite or crosslinked network, there is an inevitable reduction in other desirable properties such as modulus, strength and glass transition temperature. An alternative approach to break this paradigm is to design the chemical structure of the network to be inherently tough and strong without the need for additional modifiers [2]. This has been pursued through the incorporation of structural features that add flexibility or mobility to the polymer backbone such as increasing the molecular weight between crosslinks [2,3], blending of more flexible epoxy resins [4-6] or using more aliphatic rather than aromatic groups into the network [7,8]. While these approaches are successful, they still tend to have a deleterious impact upon other desirable properties. Another strategy and the subject of this paper has been to vary the substitution pattern of the aromatic rings from meta to para and varying the chemical linkage between the aromatic groups. Indeed, Ramsdale-Cooper et al (2018) [9] altered the aromatic substitution of the epoxide and amine groups using commercially available epoxy amine resin systems and reported higher fracture toughness for the meta substituted amine and attributed this to an internal anti-plasticisation effect and a lack of phenylene rotations within the network. Varley et al. (2019) [10] in contrast, reported improvements in fracture when tri-aryl ether tetra-functional epoxy resins were more para rather than meta substituted. It is clear however, that subtle changes in aromatic substitution and linkage groups between the aromatic groups can have a profound effect upon both the processability and properties of the cured network.

This paper compares and contrasts two recent studies [10, 11] which investigated structure property relationships in isomeric multi-aromatic amine hardeners cured with diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F.

The commercially available 4,4-diaminodiphenyl sulphone (4,4-DDS) was used as a benchmark amine from which to compare all other results. The experimental amines used were all tri-aryl amines linked with either ether or carbonyl groups and consisted of varying substitution patterns ranging from all meta (133), all para (144) and a centrally meta substituted group with two outer para substituted amines (134). The structures of the tri-aryl amines are shown in Figure 1 illustrating the systematic variation in structure.

Figure 1 Chemical structures of the tri-aryl amines used to cure the epoxy resins.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Chemicals

The epoxy resin used was diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F (BisF) obtained from Momentive Chemicals (Malaysia) (EEW 165-173 g/eq.) and degassed and dried in a vacuum oven at 90 °C for 12 hrs prior to use. The amine hardeners purchased commercially were 4,4-diaminodiphenyl sulphone (4,4-DDS) (>98%), 1,3-bis(4-aminophenoxy)benzene (134 APB), 1,4-bis(4-aminophenoxy)benzene (144 APB) and 1,3-bis(3-aminophenoxy)benzene (133 APB) were all obtained from TCI Chemicals (Japan). The ketone-linked aromatic amines 1,3-phenylene bis((3-aminophenyl) methanone) (133 BABB), 1,3-phenylenebis((4-aminophenyl) methanone) (134 BABB) and 1,4-phenylenebis((4-aminophenyl) (144 BABB), were synthesised according to methods described elsewhere [12].

2.2 Sample Preparation

Epoxy amine resin formulations were prepared using a 1:1 epoxide to amino stoichiometric mixture and blended and degassed on a rotary evaporator using an oil bath at a temperature of 110 °C. As some formulations were particularly reactive, care was taken to stop mixing immediately after the amine had fully dissolved in the epoxy resin. The resin was then poured into silicon moulds preheated at 110 °C for a minimum of 1 hr. The APB based resin systems were then cured in an air circulating oven at 110 °C for 1 hr, 140 °C for 2 hrs followed by 177 °C for 6 hrs, after which they were allowed to cool down overnight. The BABB based resin systems amines cured at 177 °C for 10 hrs and then allowed to cool down to room temperature overnight.

2.3 Characterisation

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

A Perkin-Elmer SII Seiko Instruments Sapphire differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to characterise the cure kinetics, reaction rates and glass transition temperatures of the cured networks. Using dynamic methods carried out under a nitrogen gas atmosphere the uncured resin was heated from 50 °C to 300 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min then cooled to 50 °C and ramped again to 300 °C at 10 °C/min. For samples cured in the silicon moulds in the oven, samples of cured resin of approximately 10 mg were ramped from 50 °C to 300 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min. The temperature at the peak reaction rate, T_p , for the uncured resin provided insight into the reaction rate while the endotherm in the thermograms of the cured resins was used to determine the glass transition temperature, T_g .

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA)

A Perkin-Elmer SEIKO DMA Diamond II Series was used to determine the glass transition temperature of the polymer networks. Samples of approximate dimensions 10 mm x 50 mm x 2.8 mm were placed in a dual cantilever fixture using a force amplitude of 20 μ m and a frequency of 1 Hz while increasing the temperature from 50 °C to 250 °C at a rate of 2 °C/min. The glass transition temperature, T_g , was determined from the peak in the $\tan \delta$ spectrum.

Thermogravimetric Analysis

The thermal stability of the cured samples was investigated using a Mettler Toledo 821e TGA/SDTA thermo-gravimetric analyser (TGA). About 10 mg of sample in a ceramic crucible was heated from 50 to 600 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min under a non-oxidative nitrogen environment. Samples were characterised according to the temperature at 10% mass loss, $T_{10\%}$, the temperature at the maximum rate of degradation, T_{max} , and the char yield at 600 °C.

Flexural Properties

The flexural properties were measured using an Instron 3880 Universal Testing Machine fitted with a 1 kN load cell configured in the three point bending mode. The crosshead rate used was 1 mm/min and testing continued until the sample failed. The span to depth ratio was kept constant at 16:1 and all results reported are an average of at least 3 replicates.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Processability

Dynamic DSC thermograms of the uncured BABB resins are shown in Figure 2a) which reveal large exothermic peaks typical of the epoxy amine cure reaction and are also representative of the APB resins. The thermograms immediately reveal systematic differences between the BABB hardeners in regards to the breadth of the exothermic peak and the temperature at maximum rate of cure, T_p . Interestingly, the width of the exotherm becomes narrower with increasing para substitution from 133 BABB to 144 BABB. Whilst the reasons for this are not fully understood, it may reflect the formation of a less homogenous network arising from the presence of cis and trans conformers in the 133 BABB and 134 BABB amines which are not available to the 144 BABB. Variations in T_p highlight differences in reactivity that are clearly evident in the traces. A higher T_p reflects a slower reaction, suggesting the order of reactivity of the BABB hardeners is as follows; 144 BABB is the slowest, followed by 134 BABB and then 133 BABB. Figure 2b) uses T_p to compare the rate of reaction of the BABB with the APB systems. As can be seen, overall the BABB amines are significantly slower than APB, and become less reactive as the amine becomes increasingly para substituted. This is in contrast to the APB amines which become more reactive with increasing para substitution. This contrasting behavior can be largely explained by a combination of resonance and inductive effects and the fact that ether is strongly electron donating and carbonyl is mildly electron withdrawing.

Figure 2a) Dynamic DSC thermograms of the uncured BABB and 44 DDS resins illustrating the effect of aromatic substitution on the reaction rate. b) Comparison of the effect aromatic substitution and linkage group on the T_p , during epoxy amine cure.

3.2 Thermal Properties

The elastic modulus and $\tan \delta$ spectra of the cured networks are shown in Figure 3a) and are typical of fully cured and homogenous crosslinked networks revealing clear glass transition temperatures. The APB networks have much lower T_g s than the 44 DDS due to their higher molecular weight between crosslinks and enhanced flexibility. The T_g s of the APB networks all vary systematically with aromatic substitution, increasing, with the extent of para substitution. Given no other structural variations, it can be proposed that the increasingly para substitution of the polymer backbone produces a more rigid and thermally stable structure which increases the required energy to initiate cooperative segmental motion. Again, the amine hardeners containing both ether and carbonyl are compared in Figure 3b). As can be seen, the carbonyl linked amine produces significantly higher T_g s mostly likely due to the more rigid nature of the carbonyl group producing even higher resistance to segmental motion. There is a general trend in increasing T_g with para substitution, although not completely consistent for the 134 and 144 BABB networks. Compared with 44 DDS, the APB networks have significantly lower T_g s, while the 134 and 144 BABB networks have similar T_g s. Values obtained from DMTA and DSC measurements are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Thermal analysis of the cured network including glass transition temperatures and thermal stability.

Sample	T_g (°C)		T_{max} (°C)	$T_{10\%}$ (°C)	Char at 600 °C (%)
	DSC	DMTA			
133 APB	128	130	406.2	404.7	27.3
134 APB	133	137	387.8	387.8	28.3
144 APB	135	140	385.5	386.7	28.4
133 BABB	141	154.3	395.4	380.0	45.3
134 BABB	175	172.4	399.8	403.6	40.8
144 BABB	170	171.9	393.2	396.0	46.0
44 DDS	187.5	185.2	405.7	404.5	26.7

The thermal stability of the cured BABB and 44 DDS networks as determined using TGA is illustrated by the thermograms shown in Figure 4a) which reveal a single degradation step followed by a more stable char region. In terms of the onset of degradation temperature, the 44 DDS cured network displays the greatest thermal stability as evidenced by its higher T_{max}

and $T_{10\%}$, although the char yield was significantly lower than the BABB networks. The less thermally stable BABB networks showed no evidence of any trend with aromatic substitution, which is not unexpected given that thermal stability is closely related cohesive strength which is independent of substitution patterns. The char yields for the BABB networks however, were significantly higher compared with the 44 DDS due to the production of a more highly aromatic char layer. This result provides an important indicator for their potential use as inherently fire-retardant polymer networks. Comparison of the results with the APB networks in Figure 4b) and Table 1 suggest that the thermal stabilities are similar, but the char yields for the BABB networks are again significantly higher compared with APB. Overall, the APB and BABB networks present a modestly lower thermal stability than 44 DDS which can be related to their susceptibility to thermal cleavage of the two carbonyl and oxygen linkages compared with the very stable single sulphone linkage within the 44 DDS.

Figure 3 DMTA storage modulus and $\tan \delta$ spectra of the cured APB and 44 DDS networks illustrating the impact of aromatic substitution on T_g . b) Comparison of the effect aromatic substitution and linkage group on the T_g after cure.

Figure 4 TGA thermograms of the cured BABB and 44 DDS networks illustrating the impact of aromatic substitution on thermal stability. b) Comparison of the effect aromatic substitution and linkage group on the char yield after cure.

3.3 Mechanical Properties

The impact of substitution patterns and linkage groups on the flexural mechanical properties, modulus, strength and displacement at yield are shown in Figure 5a) b) and c) respectively. The first observation from these results is that most of the network properties are significantly superior to the industry standard aromatic amine, 44 DDS. Fig. 5a) and b) reveal a general decrease in modulus and strength respectively with increasing para substitution, while the displacement at yield in Figure 5c) increases with increasing para substitution. When directly comparing the impact of carbonyl versus ether linkage groups, the carbonyl linked amines all displayed greater strengths and moduli but lower displacements at yield. These changes can be explained in terms of the chemical structure of the network and the short range molecular motions of the polymer backbone. The lack of phenylene rotations or π flips for the meta substituted amines results in a so called supplementary or molecular reinforcement which increases stiffness and strength [13,14]. For the para para substituted amines, it has been proposed that an increased ability of phenylene rotations or π flips creates an energy dissipation mechanism which increases displacement not present in the meta substituted amines. Clearly, the planar carbonyl linkages add to the molecular reinforcement for the meta substituted amines compared with the more flexible APB amines, while in the case of the para para amines, the flexible ether linked APB appears to enhance mobility to increase yield displacement compared with the more rigid carbonyl linkage.

Figure 5 Flexural properties of the BABB and APB cured networks after cure illustrating the impact upon a) flexural modulus, b) flexural strength and c) displacement at yield.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Tri-aryl ether and ketone amine isomers with varying meta and para aromatic substitution have been cured with a commercially available diglycidyl ether of biphenol F epoxy resin and compared. Systematic variations were observed in the reaction rates, which were explained in terms of a combination of inductive and resonance effects. The electron donating ether groups increase reaction rates of the amines while the electron withdrawing nature of the carbonyl groups had the opposite effect to reduce the reaction rate. Aromatic substitution positions also had a systematic impact that was controlled by the ortho and para directing nature of resonance effects. In terms of the thermal and mechanical properties, the carbonyl groups tended to increase T_g , char yield, modulus and strength whilst reducing displacement at yield. Regardless of chemical linkage, increasing para substitution increased T_g and displacement at yield, whilst reducing strength and stiffness. All changes could be attributed to local mobility within the rigid polymer network.

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